

Research Article

Strategies used by Teachers for the Teaching of Oral English in Bayelsa State
Secondary Schools

Charles-Zalakor, Lere Justina¹, Mary Allen Agih¹, and Kwaghga Beetseh^{2*}

¹Department of Arts Education, Faculty of Education, Niger Delta University
Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

²Francis Sulemanu Idachaba Library, Joseph Sarwuan Tarkaa University, Makurdi
PMB 2373 Benue State Nigeria

*Corresponding author: beetsekwaghga@gmail.com

Abstract

The paper is on strategies used by teachers for the teaching of oral English in Bayelsa state secondary schools in Nigeria. The teaching of oral English in schools aims at improving the communication, competence of the learners in a number of areas, transactional turns, pronunciation, intonation, and so on. The paper also looked at approaches to the teaching of oral English, communicative stress, transactional turn, discursal approach, description narrations and instructions, pronunciation and intonation, segmental features, supra-segmental features and intonation. Some recommendations were made, research (1) more emphasis on the teaching of oral English in our secondary schools (2) more emphasis on the use of communicative approach of English language teaching in designing the teachers syllabus.

Keyword: Strategies, Teacher, Teaching, Oral English, Bayelsa State, Secondary Schools.

Received: 11 January 2022

Accepted: 28 April 2022

Introduction

Before the Second World War, language teaching was seen as mainly the teaching of reading and writing, (Ojutesunday, 2016). This attitude changed during war because of the need for effective communication. Teaching language which was mainly reading and

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4181 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

writing with little emphasis on speaking and listening was found wanting because communication in a new language was not easily achieved. For a language to become useful as a communication medium, emphasis should be placed on speaking and listening. The four language skills should be taught at all times. According to Ojutesunday (2016), teaching of four language skills enables teaching to address both the linguistic and communicative aspects of the language.

Fumi (2013) states that interaction is important in language learning because through it, students increase their language store and they listen to and read authentic linguistics material or even the output of their fellow students in discussion, joint problem solving task or dialogue. Oral means more than referring words; it also means relating to sinterlocutor, Fumi 2013. Fumi (2013) said that language takes place in double context, on one hand, students learn words and grammatical structures that refer to an established distant culture the external context of language. On the other hand, they use words and structure to communicate with others in the classroom. The dual nature of language learning learning is the forms and how to use them demand that emphasis be placed on both reading and writing as well as on the oral aspect of language in the teaching and, learning processes.

Language learning, which is learning the structure, grammar, phonology etc, of English language should be close to “language acquisition”, a term used here to refer to a language from a very early age. Hence a classroom, speech is regarded as the foundation of language work. The reason for learning the English language in African countries is to have a second language and an international language for boarder communication. This means that the learner’s ability to express himself clearly in conversational English is an over-riding factor. The learner should be taught to perceive the various sounds of second language correctly, to be integrated into the English lessons to enable students practice the use of the language they are studying. The practice so derived would lead to communicative competence needed to enhance students’ academic performance.

Some English language teachers are not exposed to the techniques of teaching oral language in the course of their training; such teachers find it difficult to teach oral English. Some teachers who received full training on how to teach oral English do not teach it, because they are dissatisfied with the job. The resultant effect is the generally poor performance of the students in any external examinations.

The teaching of oral English in schools aims to improve the communicative turns, pronunciation, international and so on. Much as the primary function of spoken language is transactional, the important spoken language is primarily transactional. The syllabus of spoken English should therefore include short turns of transactional or international type, long turns communicative stress, international and evaluating the spoken language.

Approach to the Teaching of Oral English Interactional Short turns

According to Antonia (2007), “the conversational approach helps the learner to encounter less communicative stress”. A short turn consists of only one or two utterances. It does not demand much of the speaker as in the example below given by Igwebuiké (1996).

- C: do you like
K: it was all right
C: my mother’s favorite is daiquiri but I love whisky sour – it’s super
K: and marquerita I love as well its beautiful
C: what’s that?
K: it’s some t it’s ssertequila and line t with something else t
C: I don’t know it.

Above is an international conversation between some female students. It is an example of short – turns. In short turns situations, participating speakers end up feeling comfortable. The maintenance of social relationships is the overriding factor. Igwebuiké (1996) sum it out as being characterized by constantly shifting topics and a great deal of agreement thus.

It is a characteristic of speech of this kind that they should end up feeling comfortable with each other and friendly. It is very noticeable that speakers in such “chat” do not typically challenge each other, do not argue, and do not require repetition of something that the other person has said. If a participant in such an interaction does not hear what exactly it was the speaker said, he is quite a likely simple to nod and smile. The remarks we made about “generalized vocabulary and sparse information - packing, apply mostly to causal interactional chat. A close post-hoc analysis of what was said in such a chat often reveals quite large areas of unclarity and not specific where it seems likely that the listener, was only partially processing the message coming doing the listening equivalent of “skimming” in reading which we could characterize as listening for the gist, overall impression, rather than for the detail.

They believe that even infants learning to speak, use a good deal of interactional short turns to acquire what they want e. g cries of “ more” ice cream, ‘ no socks’. In interactional short turns, Igwebuike proposes that the learner’s language should be used to build his responses when he responds to what somebody says. Short responses are used as follow:

Can you help me?

The speaker may either agree or co-operate or not. Here are some possible responses:

Yes, of course

Right

Right, I will

Sure, of course

Sorry, I can manage it

I’m afraid not.

They mean that to elicit responses in English, the speakers also agree with what has been said by producing conversational replies rather than yes or no responses. Where the speaker wants to disagree, he does so politely by expressing his disagreement in a round-about way e.g well, not, not quite, no erm, I don’t know, etc.

Or may dedicate possible doubt as in; I’m not quite sure

Really

Is that right

Is that so? Etc

For the learner to give these varied responses, he has to be able to express both good and bad opinions e.g

Very nice

Very good

Really nice

Not very nice

Quite nice

Not very nice

Not at all etc.

The background knowledge of a similar expression in the learner's mother-tongue helps the student in producing sentences. The speaker also needs "filler" which will help him to plan what he says.g "well" "erm" " or " interspersed with pauses. The learners also need a set of vocabulary good, easy, etc. as well as a few simple structures such as I think; of course: etc.

Communicative stress

According to Igwebuiké (1996), communicative stress conditions in which the learners feel more comfortable in producing what he has to say and conditions under which he feels less comfortable. Communicative is eliminated when a speaker is speaking to a junior or peer. He is also naturally comfortable when he talks to one listener in a familiar or private environment. He is also comfortable when he speaks to a listener who understands the target language as much as he does and when the information he has is of a familiar sort he understands it very well. It is also easier for the speaker to give an account of a series of events than it is to provide an argument for why those events occurred in that order.

The learner will encounter some uncomfortable conditions when he is required to stand up and tell the class what happened last week, since he would not be able to tell what background knowledge the teacher and the other members of the class have, he will also have problems of using the appropriate language. Another level of difficulty is when the learner has to address a group of five or seven other students. According to Igwebuiké, the learner should be encouraged to use English direct expression like this, that, there, over there, and other phrases like -This one on top, the red one, etc. gradually when the

students will learn less support, he would now rely on the English language alone to express what he means.

Igwebuiké (1996;15) suggest that the teachers provide some required vocabulary while the students monitor their problems and how to say things they want to say but do not know-how. In a situation like this, the teacher puts the student in a position where he is required to communicate for a purpose and help him to have minimal communicative stress by not pushing down his ideas or corrections on the learner.

Transactional Turn

Transactional long turns are made up of a string of utterances that may last long. What is required of a speaker in a long turn is considerably more demanding than what is required of a speaker in a long turn takes responsibility for creating a structured sequence of utterances which must help the listener to create a coherent mental representation of what he is trying to say,.

The teacher is to help the learner by providing coherent structured sentences that are clear and specify any relevant .properties needed for classification. From here the learner will move on to say what happens if he is recounting a narrative. He will then establish where and when the events happened and who the main participants were, before he recounted the series of event in the order in which they happened or, if for some reason he chooses not to do this he must explicitly mark the deviation from this unmarked ordering.

Much as short turns give excellent development in the acquisition of language skills in the early stage of learning a language, exclusion concentration on short turns throughout the curriculum will yield speakers who are not able to take part in a normal conversation. Learners need a model in the early stage and they should notice the way the native speaker “use manipulatively explanatorily, to communicate with and makeup what they say as they go along” Learners are expected to “control a range of abilities from making short turns in primary interactions “chats” to taking longer interactional turns” in spoken production. Since native speakers rarely produce complete correct sentences in spoken language, they believe that foreign students should not be obliged to do so all the time. “It may be necessary to bring to his attention what happens in his native language since our knowledge of such communicative matters is usually held well below the level of our consciousness. Listening analytically to a tape of what goes on in the student’s native language may be a valuable preamble to listening to a similar tape in the target language

may be modeled more or less directly on his native language experience and on the tapes which he hears in listening comprehension classes”

In the teaching of transactional turns, the authors suggest that explicit teaching of the production of the spoken form of the foreign language should be particularly concerned with the teaching of extended transactional turns, (Egele 2016:95)

For one reason, because there are likely to prove difficult for most speakers, for another, because foreign students visiting native speaking English country will have to ‘cope’ in an industrialized, bureaucratized society which depends very much on the ability of individuals to use spoken language to communicate information efficiently; for yet another reason, because foreign students who required English out of a native speaking context are likely to require English primarily for transactional reasons, for acquiring and disseminating information and lastly it is methodologically much more feasible to teach control of transaction turns.

In transactional turns, the speaker would need to express that she is saying a great deal more clearly, and her listener would probably keep on interrupting to check that she understood who was doing what, to whom, at any given point in the summary, (Egele, 2016:96). In interactional turns, details are not necessary, and ‘chat’ is characterized by shifting topic and a great deal of agreement on them”.

The authors further suggest that advanced learners should be exposed to a range of models an unreasonable “non-native” standard of ‘correctness’ in all situations.

The teacher probably tries to achieve the set of phonology contrasts that is manipulated in R.P but does not worry too much about the phonetic details. He ignores delicacies like where about and ‘r’ is produced and whether and ‘L’ is light or dark and is simply grateful if the student can pronounce an opposite between ‘L’ and ‘r’ after all there are native accents of British English which manifest uvular ‘r’ light ‘L’ (Egele, 2016:28).

TRANSACTIONAL TASK

According to Egele (2016), teaching this skill should be in the context of a specific we can bring the analytical technique to bear on the task of different types and on different conditions under which the students may be asked to perform the task and we can, in principle, construct a course graded in term of difficulty. In the transactional task,

communicative stress is examined. What are the conditions which relate to communicative stress? They include the following:

(1) Features Of The Context

- (i) The listener- it is easy for the speaker if the listener is one of his peers or 'junior' to him. It is easier to talk to one listener than many.
- (ii) The situation - it is easier for the speaker if he is speaking in a familiar, private environment.

(2) State of knowledge of the listener

- (i) The language - it is helpful for the speaker if the listener knows as much of the target language as the speaker does.
- (ii) The information - it is helpful for the speaker if he has information if the listener for some reason, needs. This puts the speaker firmly in control of the information and motivates him to communicate that information.

(3) Types of Task

- (i) Status of knowledge - it is helpful for the speaker if the information he has control of is helpful if he is familiar with the foreign language vocabulary which is essential to the completion of the task.
- (ii) The structure of the task provides its structure so that the task. Thus, it is easier for any speaker to give an account of a series of events than it is to provide an argument for why those events occurred in that order.

In interactional conversation, details are not given. On the other hand, in interactional conversation, the details of what happened are important. Again in interactional conversation, the setting is always explicit. e.g.

'I was watching TV last night' does not specify when or what happened (Igwebuike, 1996)
In transactional conversation, details are important. e.g.

We do not assume a lot of shared knowledge because the listener should understand what is being said: (Igwebuike 1996: 19).

To explain a situation, the speaker has to extract a structured event. This structuring is a cognitive task, not a linguistic task.

The stereotype of events or situations would be used as props by teachers to establish an appropriate language for the learner to express or give details of a situation. If for instance a picture is given and the students are to name all the objects will score high. If on the other hand, they are to identify the relevant features, a different skill is needed not just for naming but also for determining the objects to be named-abilities to extract the relevant salient 'facts' from a mass of details communicative skill.

The cognitive load is described as the complicating factor. "t is the ability to use language adequately which is at issue rather than simply knowing the forms of the language". The teacher is to use the event-structure and different stereotypes in teaching: the interpretation of the language by using the background of the cultural stereotypes that lie behind the native speaker's language. Apart from the socio-cultural stereotypes, there is the Eye-witness account.

Problems of International Short Turns/ Transactional Turns

According to Igwebuike (1996), it is difficult to communicate in a foreign language aimed with only short sentences. Students should be exposed to video and tape recordings of naturally occurring conversations but not for a long time. They give practice to particular features thereby leading to the production of boring conversation. Another problem is the sentence structures which have traditionally been the concern of 'short turns' approaches. These do not allow native speakers to inventive and flexible use of language to cope with the demands of the communicative situation. It is in principle hard to sustain institutionalized 'chat' for the timetable period, since the topic of conversation may wander too wide for the junior partners to understand enough to justify the senior partner's effort. The opportunity for practice if the teacher is the only 'senior' available is limited. A problem of transactional turns is the difficulty in the competent and flexible exploitation of limited language to make clear what is happening and who is doing what to whom.

Discoursal Approach

According to Igwebuike (1996), the teacher must observe sentence structures which have traditionally been the concern of 'short turns' approaches, and how native speakers inventively and flexibly use the language to cope with the demands of the communicative situation. Igwebuike (1996), suggested that the teacher can deliberately select the level of difficulty that he wished his students to be able to cope with and train them to that level of ability. The learner is to notice not just how the native speakers use the language but also the different aspects of the discoursal control expected of the speakers. The learner

is expected to maintain the same description of the entity. Teachers are two competing same-gender referents.

Success teaching of discursual competence demands of the teachers that he/she should analyze the language which native speakers use in discourse so that he can ensure that realistic models are presented for his students to imitate and base their performances on. In producing discursual of the sort, we have been assuming that the speaker uses to describe, narrate, instruct, etc. are all strategies which are available to him in his native language. We are assuming that it is not the job of the foreign language teacher to teach those basic skills. Rather it is the teacher's job to provide the students with the necessary language to make those skills work in English.

Descriptive, Narrative, and Instructions

Description and instructions have a lot in common because they impose a temporal structure upon a collection of objects which are not intrinsically temporally instructed. The teacher gives the kind of exercise in which language is used flexibly not the 'correct' vocabulary type. Here the learner come up with an adequate description which helps in identifying what he is talking about. Francis (2001), stated that both the narrative and descriptive methods can be graded under fewer simpler, which are easy to describe, and more complex pieces that are difficult to describe.

In narrative sequence, there is the possibility of grading the cognitive and the linguistic load-differences in the gender pronouns are easier than when the gender of the referent in his narration is the same. The speaker is expected to choose a distinguishing feature for the individuals and maintain these features.

Considering a story which first depicts an elderly woman sitting in a kitchen reading a book (house-wife), then moves to an event concerning a beautiful young girl in a chamber (a princess) and then returns to a woman in the kitchen again.

In describing the scenes, two native speakers characterize the individuals differently using different vocabulary but they distinguish between them as (woman/princess), (mother/beautiful woman), (Francis, 2001:67), one problem with introducing two same-type participants into a story is that the speaker needs to maintain a consistent distinction between them. The speaker has to be consistent in his use of lexical expressions and be careful in his use of pronominal expressions. Communicative stress load looked at from the point of cognitive difficulty is increased as same-gender referents included.

In narration, the cognitive load is identified as the complicating factors, rather than the linguistic forms. Relevant features of the setting and being and to identify participants and maintain the spate identity of the participants are taught and tested. The events-structured description which many contribute to its relative ease or difficulty includes whether the setting maintained throughout the story and what are the implications of the change of place for the story. Where there is a change of place setting. For a foreign learner to be able to interpret what is going on in this sequence, he must be able to use the implications of place and their consequent indications of time in the same way as the native speaker, (Francis 2001). It seems more valuable for the teacher to use the British background and culture course to explore the socio-cultural stereotypes.

In describing same gender objects, the learner has to maintain the same description of the entity and has to use a pronominal form when it is clear which entity to pronounce refers to. Students may be advised never to use pronominal forms where two competing same-gender references are. One uses pronominal forms to refer back to the last-mentioned participants. In other words, as soon as a new participant until an even never participant is introduced. The teacher is advised to analyze which the native speaker used in discourse so that he can ensure that reasonable and realistic models are represented for students to imitate and base their performance on. These discursal strategies which the speaker uses to describe, instruct and narrate, are assumed to be available to the learner in his narrative language. The teacher is to provide the students with the necessary language to develop the skills while the mother-language teacher is to teach the skills.

Pronunciation and intonation

According to Ituen (1998), to organize the content of the pronunciation syllabus, the following must be considered:

- (1) Segmental features of vowels, consonants syllabus boundaries involving problems with junctures e.g. 'ice cream I scream' etc. according to Ituen (1998), the vowel is a sound produced with free flow of air and there are the cardinal vowels (Primary and secondary). The primary vowel I, e, E, a, are unrounded while the secondary vowels are the distinct sound of vowels and final positions. According to Ituen (1998), words that have similar sounds may co-occur in utterances and unless they are pronounced properly they will lose their meaning e.g.
 - (a) The heat /i:/ was bad (b) the hit /i/ was bad (c) the height /ai/ was bad (d) The hut /^/ was bad (e) The heart /a:/ was bad (f) The hurt /:/ was bad.

A syllable is a unit of sound produced, with a puff of breath. He goes further by saying that for better articulation end of the syllable and the beginning of another should be well-known. He says that when the letter “r” ends a spelling of a word and the following word begins with a vowel, a /r/ sound is heard and that some words do not receive primary stress in connected speech with English and these are known as the weak forms

In linking words these examples are given:

/t/ /e rent e /b|3E/

Law and order

/L : ren : d
D D d

While examples of weak forms are;

I can see /ð/kðensi:/, (ʊ30-makuri 1996:9)

- (iii) Supra-segment features (stress, rhythm, intonation) if defined this way, the teacher will be able to focus on the individual units of the sound of remedial and reinforcement purposes. The students will acquire linguistic competence (Francis, 2001)

Segmental features

Contractive analysis procedures help to identify pronunciation difficulties in:

- (1) Articulation of sounds
- (2) Distribution of sounds
- (3) Differences between phonemes allophones in the mother-tongue and the target language system e.g.

In Bayelsa State, the Izon languages have difficulty articulating words ‘jucst and gist, Church, Jump, shop, and chop.

The contractive analysis of English and Izon reveals that certain consonants which occur in Izon language include: /j/, /G/, /ch/, /sh/, and /th/. This means that when a native speaker of Izon language wants to pronounce English words containing these five sounds, he is likely to substitute Izon consonants which are as close as possible to the English ones, thus, he may substitute Izon /3/ for the English /j/, Izon /z/ for /c/ /dz/ which are palate-alveolar consonants cluster, cause problem to many whose language, have different syllable structure with the

target language. The learner often introduces a vowel between the consonants e.g. 'electric' becomes 'eletriki', 'school' becomes 'sukulu'. This causes spelling | meaning problems. Apart from these phonetic difference problems, there are also problems caused by a confusion of the vowel phonemes in two words concerned e.g. "seating" arrangement is arrangement for sitting. According to Ituen (1998), some pronunciations examples are

seat	sit		
keel	kill		
cheep	chip i.e	sip	cip
sheep	ship -	seep	cip

Suprasegmental features:

These are stress, rhythm and intonation. These influence and modify segmental features, vowels, in particular, (Francis, 2001)

- (1) Stress: according to Ituen (1998), stress is the degree of force with which a sound or syllable is uttered. English is stress-timed and the stress and unstressed syllables in words and sentences are familiar to the same amount of stress in Nigerian languages. To teach stress, the teacher should look at the words of two, three four, or more syllables. The first syllable ('master') on the second syllable (confront) etc.
- (2) Some words can be used as both nouns and verbs on the second syllable e.g nouns 'import, 'increase, 'conduct
- (3) Word groups: the word group in which the nouns is modified by other words retains its normal stress pattern e.g
a 'red bad
a 'red door

If the modifier and noun from a regular collocation as one word, the modifier is stressed differently e.g 'Brilliant students'

I can 'swim 'very well.

- (4) Weak vowels: Several pronouns and auxiliary verbs are normally unstressed in English. Examples of unstressed vowels are found in 'and' but, from, to the vowels in the words above are stressed. In a sentence like 'we're in it, full stress on the pronoun "it" distorts the vowel quality by changing short /i:/
- (5) Rhythm: the cumulative effect on the stress system of a language makes up its rhythm. The sound pattern which its parallel forms and repetition of words,

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4181 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

capture the rhythm of oral English. It shows each group of stressed and unstressed syllables as in roughly the same line. This is why English is called a stress-timed rather than a syllable-timed language. Learners whose mother-tongues are syllable-timed need a lot of practice in mastering the rhythm of English.

Intonation

In English, intonation does not change the meaning of words as in the case of Izon, rather it affects the entire sentence, (Francis, 2001).

- (i) Falling tune: falling tune, occur at the end of the statement, commands and questions e.g here are some books (statement) come and see it now (command). Where do we go from here? (wh-question).
- (ii) Rising tune: rising tune occurs at the end of the sentence e.g do you come here often? A rising tune is used at the end of the utterances used when been polite e.g pass the salt, please.

Would you like some tea?

I'd like some help if you don't mind.

Interaction of supra-segmental features: stress and intonation are said to interact in various ways to modify the underlying meaning of sentences e.g (a) An unstressed syllable at the beginning of a sentence is uttered in a low tune. A stressed syllable following this stressed syllable is given a high tune. (b) Changes in intonations usually occur on stressed syllables. (c) an unstressed syllable is normally given the same tune as the stressed syllable preceding it. E.g are you coming to my birthday party tomorrow. 'Are is not stressed and it is on low tune. 'you, 'compare the area where intonation changes are affected. The rising tune on-row' at the end of the sentence is not fully stressed (Francis, 2001).

Variations in stress and intonation are important features in:

- (1) Utterances of contrast:
I want a ball not pencil
- (2) Listing of items e.g given are some salt, some pepper an egg.
- (3) In emphasizing individual words in sentences
- (4) In change mean
- (5) Stress combines with intonation to change nuances meaning without having new words to an utterance.

- (6) You can use stress to convey meaning attitudinal and correct rising and falling intonation. Oral English is taught in order to promote competence at the receptive level thereby, enhancing the communicative competence of learner.

Conclusion

Language sounds are just part of the totality of sounds in the universe. Sounds are produced when people clap, sing, clap or laugh when human beings communicate with one another they usually do that are associated with meaning. Knowledge of a language, therefore, presupposed knowledge of speech sounds combined to form meaningful utterances.

When one speaks, one produces a chain of speech which are arranged in sequences to give syllables or words. But the feature of stress and intonation are necessary for the proper functioning of these sounds in the actual speech process. In other words, the speech sounds of English and features of stress and intonation constitute the sound system in English. Teachers teaching English should teach the students properly to know the organs of speech and processes involved in speech production (Agu, 2012).

Methods of teaching oral English should be redesigned to go beyond “speech work” to speak the language. Speech work deals mainly with distinct items. Encourage students to practice the correct use of intonation, the right pronunciation of words, and a group of words.

Recommendations

From the discussion, the following recommendations are made

- (1) More emphasis on the teaching of oral English in secondary schools by English teachers
- (2) More emphasis on the use of communicative approach of English language teaching in designing the teacher’s syllabus.
- (3) Lesson “on speaking” should be planned like the other aspects the language skill such as “reading”, “comprehension”, “composition” and so on.

References

Agu, M.N (2012). Indigenous language as effective communication tool for political stability in Nigeria, *Lapai journal of central Nigeria history: Lapai Journal of the Department of History and Archeology, Ibrahim Badamasi Babagida University Niger State*. 6(1): 99-105.

Anthonia N.M, (2007). *Defining linguistic competence and communicative competence: principles and practice of teaching English as second language*, Lagos, Vitamin Educational Book.

Engele, A.F (2016). *The language teacher and wash back: focus on the senior secondary school certificate examination (SSCE) English paper: language Education, arts and social science education in Nigeria*, Ibadan: Global Academic Group Online Academic Resources.

Francis, R.U (2014). *English grammar: and phonetics* Port Harcourt, Pre-Joe Publishers.

Francis R.U (2001). *English grammar*: Port Harcourt Pre-Joe Publishers

Fumi, A (2013). *Introducing linguistics*, Port Harcourt: Sieved Ventures, Plot 24 Market Lane, Rumuola

Igwebuike, S.N (1996). *The study of the strategies used by teachers of the teaching of oral English in ObiaAkpo secondary school*. University of Port Harcourt unpublished thesis, University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt.

Ituen, A.U (1998) *Teaching secondary level English* Port Harcourt Sambros Printing Works.

Ojutesunday, A.O (2016) *fundamentals of curriculum theory and development*, Port Harcourt; Emmanest Ventures Publication Uzo-mekufi N. (1996). *An advanced English grammar and usage*: Aba, Ninlan Books

Rivers, W.M. (1987). *Interactive language teaching*: Chicago Press.